

Utilization of produced water of oil and gas exploitation for agricultural development in Muara Enim district, south Sumatera

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ABSTRACT

Besides producing crude oil and gas as the main drilling product, PT. Medco Energi Indonesia in several drilling wells in Indonesia also produces water by-products. Data from the exploitation of several oil and gas drilling wells owned by PT. Medco Energi Indonesia, shows that total crude oil production of 30,000 Barrels per day, 270,000 Barrels per day has been produced which is equivalent to 43,000,000 liters of water. This volume of produced water has not been utilized for agricultural development. The purpose of research was to identify and characterize the land and socio-economic survey to find out the problems, obstacles and opportunities for agricultural development in the area around Singa well, Lematang Exploitation Block, Muara Enim Regency, South Sumatra. The results of the discharge analysis show that the produced water is around 1.48 liters/second which is estimated to be sufficient to irrigate 2.5 hectares of land. Soil chemical analysis showed that the soil reacts acidic with a pH range between 4.17-4.66, contains low in C-organic, essential nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, sulfur), CEC, micro nutrients (Mn, Cu, Zn), except high iron content. This produced water requires management with appropriate technology to increase organic matter content of around 5%, increase pH more than 5.0, increase nutrient levels by applying fertilizer sourced from outside the plant system. For developing lowland organic vegetables, 40-60 tons/ha of organic fertilizer is needed without additional inorganic fertilizers such as Urea, SP-36, KCl, sulfur or micro fertilizers.

Key word: oil and gas exploitation, produced water, characteristics of land and water resources, agricultural development

INTRODUCTION

Oil and gas exploitation by PT. Medco Energi Internasional Tbk is carried out in several drilling wells in Indonesia to produce crude oil and gas as the main product of drilling, and liquid waste. Liquid waste is in the form of produced water with a debit of 270,000 Barrel per day which is equivalent to a volume of 43 million liters per day (Anonymous, 2010). This liquid waste

potentially pollute the surface water environment and then poison agricultural crops if the water is directly used as irrigation water without physical or chemical anticipation. Besides plants, humans also have potentially to cause wastewater poisoning due to heavy metal content.

Heavy metals in produced wastewater are caused by the operation of power plants and other industrial facilities that can release harmful inorganic chemicals such as Cyanide (CN), Boron (B), Copper (Cu), Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd) through direct release or through a cooling system into aquatic ecosystems and soil around industrial sites (Susana and Ricky, 2009). Some of these heavy metals are needed by plants to carry out biological metabolism in the process of growth and production of carbohydrates, but generally carried out in small amounts so that the presence of industrial waste tends to poison the plants because the consequences in irrigation water and soil are generally excessive.

Especially for Boron (B), it is generally in the form of boric acid (H_2BO_3) and $B(OH)_4$ borate hydrate ion. Plants need it to metabolize nucleic acids, carbohydrates, proteins, phenols, auxins, and cell division and prolongation. Required in small amounts, absorbed by plant roots through the mechanism of mass flow and diffusion. The threshold value of boron concentration in irrigation water is 1.0 mg/L. Soils with high levels of carbon dioxide (Al^{3+} and Fe^{3+} high levels) such as acidic dry soil generally bind boron strongly chemically through a C-specific bonding process and will release it into the soil solution slowly if the bond saturation limit is exceeded (Nurhayati, 2010). This suggests that Boron (B) poisoning is stronger and longer danger in acidic dry land ecosystems.

Measurement results during field orientation indicate that the produced water discharge in the Gas Mining Unit is about 1.48 liters /second, a volume that is estimated to be sufficient to irrigate 2.5 hectares of farmland. Factors that must be estimated in the utilization of produced water are the physical, chemical and biological water quality that must fulfill the standard so that the plants do not experience poisoning (Rejekiningrum et al., 2011).

The production of waste produced water, the P.T Medco Gas Production Unit South Sumatra has been processed liquid waste through a network of chemical treatment plants. This chemical treatment aims to remove particles that are not non-precipitated (colloids), heavy metals, phosphorus compounds, and toxic organic substances by applying certain chemicals. The provision of these ingredients in principle takes place through changes in properties, namely from not easily precipitated to easily precipitated (flocculation-coagulation) either with or without an oxidation-reduction reaction (Anonymus, 2010). Sampling of water that has been treated chemically periodically and analysis in the

laboratory is the next step to ensure that the produced water is safe for the environmental surface and soil water around the location.

The factory management policy to utilize water that has been treated chemically as a source of irrigation water for the community around the factory is a pioneering activity in the field of agriculture partnership with farmer groups in the villages around the factory. If possible, the use of water is not only for agriculture but also for household activities, especially in the dry season when people find it difficult to get clean water. With regard to agricultural business, the development of organic farming is a suitable alternative both in terms of land fertility status, human resources (farmers and factory employees), and the potential for organic fertilizer procurement. In addition, the health world is developing the issue of healthy food because of the many cases of low quality food as a result of the use of inorganic fertilizers and pesticides.

Organic cultivation systems are defined as processes that pay attention to the environment (environmentally friendly), starting from the production stage to yield processing. So organic farming is not only limited to its products, but in the process of sending it to the last consumer (Husnain et al.2005).Thus, organic cultivation does not use mineral fertilizers and artificial pesticides, only depends on organic materials and recycling (Rigby and Caceres 2001).Improving soil fertility, better selling price and income, better and healthier rice quality and less pest and diseases attack were the most benefits got from the conversion to semi and fully organic rice farming system (Sukristiyonubowo et al., 2011).

Based on the results of the identification and preliminary study, the produced water at PT Medco Energi Internasional Tbk will be applied for the development of organic agriculture. Therefore, research activities are needed related to efforts to utilize produced water from oil and gas wells for the development of organic agriculture. Figure 1presents an illustration of the utilization of produced water from oil and gas exploitation.

Figure 1. Illustration of utilization of produced water from oil and gas exploitation

The objectives of the research activities were (1) to identify and characterize the land around Singa well, Lematang exploitation block, Muara Enim Regency, South Sumatra, and (2) to conduct a socio-economic survey to find out problems, obstacles and opportunities for farming development in the area around Singa well.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and Tools

The research was carried out at Singa Well, Blok Exploitation Lematang, Muara Enim District, South Sumatra in 2011.

Materials used were (1) rainfall data from the nearest rainfall station, (2) quantity and quality of produced water from oil drilling wells, (3) soil sample data, (4) topographic data, and (5) social economy data.

The tools used were (1) GPS navigation, to determine geographical position, (2) ring sampler, (3) infiltrometer, (4) a set of laboratory tools for analysis of soil and water.

Methods

Land Characterization and Identification

Activities carried out on land identification included (1) conducting topographic surveys (elevation mapping), (2) carrying out soil sampling, and (3) carrying out water sampling.

Topographic surveys were carried out using Total Station (Figure 2). This tool was used to measure the elevation difference between two points that were between 5 m to 1 km. Unlike the theodolite which works manually, this tool works automatically so that measurements can be done quickly and

accurately. Topographic measurements were carried out to calculate the slope of the land and measure contours to compile a map of the locations to be developed for agriculture and to determine the design of supplementary irrigation.

Water sampling was carried out in 4 (four) points, namely: (1) concentrate water, (2) produced water, (3) processing pond (5th pond), and (4) final produced water storage pond. While the soil samples were taken in 5 (five) locations, namely: (1) sediment soil samples in ASRY, (2) in the Sari Wangi farmer group, (3) in the Sari Ayu farmer group, (4) in the Tani Sari Ganda Pemekaran farmer group, and (5) in rubber gardens, each at a depth of 0-20 cm, 20-40 cm.

Figure 2. Measurement of soil contours with Total Station

Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) Survey

The PRA survey was conducted through direct interviews with farmers to quickly find out the farming management in the research area. The interviews focused on the following questions: (1) Identification of agricultural problems globally (during planting, planting, and post-planting), (2) Identification of plants commonly cultivated by farmers, (3) Identification of farming management, (4) Identification of irrigation techniques (source, distribution, dosage) and (5) training (type of training). The PRA survey was attended by 30 participants, consisting of 18 male farmers, including the village head of Bangun Sari, the village chief of Suka Menanti, and 12 female farmers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PRA Survey Results

The results of the PRA survey for the identified components, namely water, farming, and institutions are described as follows:

1. Water

- a. Water sources for household and farming needs come from wells, rivers, rain and springs.
- b. Water shortages generally occur in July to September, with the peak of August
- c. Water problems are poor quality of well water, lack of costs to build wells individually, to build wells collectively often creates potential conflicts, to make a wellbore impossible because of oil in the soil
- d. There is an opportunity for the use of produced water, if the water quality is good (after being analyzed), farmers will use it to fulfill drinking water, domestic, and farming needs.

2. Farming

The type of business that farmers want to develop:

- a. Rubber and oil palm nurseries
- b. Fisheries and livestock
- c. Lowland vegetable farming (chili, tomato, aubergine, long bean, water spinach, spinach, etc.)
- d. Problems faced by all farmers are water, land, source & quality of seeds/seeds, business capital, cultivation technology, marketing.

3. Institutional

- a. Existing farming institutions are not optimal
- b. The existing problems that in the past were that there were farmer groups specifically for food crops, fisheries, livestock (instructions from the president of the underdeveloped village 1993-1995) were now inactive, PPLs rarely went to villages, existing farmer groups (oil palm farmer groups), lack of counseling and assistance.
- c. Farmers really want the farmer group that once existed to be active again.
- d. Existing farming institutions need to be optimized through training and mentoring

Topographic Survey Results

Figure 3 presents topographic survey results for the design of organic farming demonstration plots in the Sari Wangi and Sari Indah farmer groups. Figure 3 shows the elevation difference between one point and another on an area of 0.9 ha. It is seen that the elevation ranges from 72.5 to 76.5 m above sea level. The irrigation technique that will be developed is funjet sprayer by installing PVC pipes through excavation of PVC pipelines and installation of irrigation emitters. Furthermore, the PE pipe is installed in the middle of the field and between the lines of the plant. The water tank is planned to be installed in the southwest. Water from the source is flowed by gravity through the PVC pipe to the reservoir/tower/water tank. Furthermore, it is distributed to plants by gravity with a pump.

Figure 3. Design of organic farming demonstration plot

Results Analysis of Water and Soil Samples

The results of chemical analysis of water samples show that produced water fulfill water quality standards for irrigation, raw water, and fresh water (Table 1). Physical parameters for sludge levels were recorded at 8.0 mg/l, below the threshold allowed for irrigation water, raw water, and fresh water with a range between 1000-1500 mg/L. The degree of acidity indicated by the pH value ranges from 6.35 to 6.95, according to the pH requirement for irrigation water, raw water, and fresh water. Iron, magnesium and manganese cations are not contained in produced water at the site of the final treatment pond. Chlorine anion levels (0.32 mg/l), phosphate (0.02 mg/l), and sulfate (29.7 mg/l) lower than the threshold value. Heavy metal levels poisoning plants such as mercury

(nd), cyanide (0.07 mg/l), lead (nd), manganese (0.00 mg/l), copper (0.00 mg/l), zinc (0.02 mg/l), chromium (nd), cadmium (0.00 mg/l) below the threshold value for irrigation water, raw water, and fresh water. Salt levels are indicated by sodium content (0.22 mg/land SAR value (3.11-4.40 me/l) below the threshold value for irrigation water, raw water, and fresh water. Boron (B) is the only problem because the level is around 3.90 mg/l which exceeds the threshold value for irrigation water. To reduce the level of boron to tolerant for plants need a little treatment of lime on the pipe/irrigation channel.

The results of soil chemical analysis showed that the soil reacts acidic with a pH range between 4.17-4.66; low C-organic; low nitrogen, phosphor, potassium, and sulfur; cation exchange capacity (CEC) is low. Micro nutrients such as Mn, Cu and Zn are low except for high levels of iron (Table 2).

In the aspect of fertility, the land in the research location is categorized as marginal land which is a general character of land that has undergone further weathering. Such lands require proper technology management by focusing on increasing levels of soil organic matter to around 5%, increasing pH to > 5.0, increasing nutrient levels with fertilizers sourced from outside soil-crop systems. Due to the development of organic lowland vegetable farming, it is necessary to add organic fertilizers around 40-60 tons/ha without any additional inorganic fertilizers such as Urea, SP-36, KCl, sulfur, or micro fertilizers.

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Table 1. The produced water quality of Gas Production Unit PT. Medco Energi InternasionalTbk in South Sumatra

Parameter	Unit	Produced Water	Drinking Water	Clean Water	Raw Water	Irrigation Water
The amount of dissolved solids	mg/l	8,0	1000	1500	1000	
pH		6.3-6.95	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.0	6-9	5-9
Aluminium (Al ³⁺)	mg/l	0.00	0.2			
Ammonia (NH ₄ ⁺)	mg/l	??	1.5		0.5	
Iron (Fe ²⁺)	mg/l	3.51	0.3	1.0	0.3	0.3
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	mg/l	0.02				
Calcium (Ca ²⁺)	mg/l	0.00				
Carbondioxide (CO ₂)	mg/l	0.32				
Chloride (Cl)	mg/l		250	600	600	
Water Hardness /Amount	mg/l	0.00	500	500	500	
Magnesium (Mg ²⁺)	mg/l	0.00				
Manganese (Mn ²⁺)	mg/l	0.06-0.39	0.1	0.5	0.1	2.0
Nitrate (N)	mg/l		50	10	10	
Nitrite (N)	mg/l	0.00-0.02	3	10	0.06	5.0
Phosphate (HPO ₄ ³⁻)	mg/l	TTD				0.2
Mercury (Hg ²⁺)	mg/l	0.24-29.7	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.005
Sulphate (SO ₄ ²⁻)	mg/l		250	400	400	
Remaining Chlor (Cl ₂)	mg/l		0.3			
Cyanide (CN ⁻)	mg/l	TTD	0.07	0.1	0.02	
Lead (Pb ²⁺)	mg/l	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.03	1.0
Manganese (Mn)	mg/l	0.00				2.0
Copper (Cu)	mg/l	0.01-0.02				0.2
Zinc (Zn)	mg/l	TTD				2.0
Chrome (Cr)	mg/l	0.00				1.0
Cadmium (Cd)	mg/l	0.00				0.01
Arsenic (As)	mg/l	0.00				1.0
Selenium (Se)	mg/l	TTD				0.05
Nickel (Ni)	mg/l	3.90				5.0
Boron (B)	mg/l	0.22				1.0
Sodium (Na)	me/l	3.11-4.40				60
SAR	me/l					10-18
Sodium carbonate residue	mg/l					1.25-2.50
Organic substances (KMnO ₄)	mg/l		10	10		
Dissolved oxygen (DO)	mg/l				< 6.0	
BOD	mg/l				2.0	
COD	mg/l					
Detergent	mg/l		0.5	0.5	0.5	
Coli group 36°C	/100 ml		0	10	1000	
E. Coli 44°C	/100 ml		0	0	100	

Table 2. Chemical properties of soil samples at the demonstration plot

Parameter	Soil Sample									
	S2A 0-20	S2A 20-40	S2B 0-20	S2B 20-40	S3 0-20	S3A 0-20	S3A 20-40	S4 20-40	S5 0-20	S5 20-40
pH (1:5):										
H ₂ O	4,20	4,70	4,23	4,43	4,44	4,17	4,31	4,20	4,66	4,64
KCl	3,84	3,93	3,86	3,88	3,87	3,92	3,98	3,85	4,00	4,00
Organic Mater:										
C-organic (%)	2,03	1,80	1,72	1,21	0,83	0,83	0,68	0,72	1,76	0,89
N (%)	0,15	0,13	0,15	0,11	0,11	0,06	0,08	0,09	0,13	0,10
C/N (%)	14	14	11	11	8	13	9	8	14	9
P ₂ O ₅ -Bray (mg/kg)	2,09	5,73	3,66	1,05	0,78	1,30	1,04	0,53	3,14	1,04
HClExtract25%:										
P ₂ O ₅ (mg/100g)	5,32	5,58	4,80	4,01	3,19	2,12	2,13	2,41	4,27	2,66
K ₂ O (mg/100g)	3,82	2,81	2,39	1,51	1,65	0,90	0,61	1,06	1,95	0,61
Morgan										
VenemaExtract:	45,56	39,3	42,58	26,86	20,1	13,5	10,24	13,69	16,9	10,26
K ₂ O (mg/kg)	0,00	0,47	0,00	0,00	9	3	59,67	16,74	7	0,00
S (mg/kg)					0,00	0,93			0,47	
Am.AsetatExtra										
ct1 pH 7:	8,72	7,42	6,92	7,73	6,34	4,17	4,49	7,21	5,95	4,64
CEC (Cmol(+))/kg)										
DTPAExtract:										
Fe (mg/kg)	185,3	273,1	117,6	83,4	33,8	26,3	14,7	16,9	85,7	19,3
Mn (mg/kg)	6,66	5,48	4,11	2,66	2,29	0,94	0,86	0,80	4,22	0,70
Cu (mg/kg)	1,68	1,68	0,97	0,31	0,31	1,21	1,02	1,39	1,30	0,88
Zn (mg/kg)	0,80	0,36	0,25	0,15	0,15	0,29	0,34	0,24	0,29	0,06

Based on the initial field orientation, it is known that the land slopes around 6%, so conservation is needed to prevent loss of nutrients through erosion and surface runoff. Therefore, vegetative erosion control will be carried out by making porch terrace reinforced with terrace reinforcement plants such as fodder grass (setaria, elephant grass, king grass) or vetiver plants. There is a relationship between horizontal width with different elevations (vertical distance) so that erosion does not occur on sloping land such as at the current research location. Based on the general formula, the width of the field of land is calculated by the following equation:

$$H_1 = \frac{V_1}{Slope}$$

Where:

H1 = Horizontal Interval (width of processing area)

V1 = Vertical Interval (difference in elevation between processing area)

Slope = Slope (percent)

If the slope is 6%, and the vertical distance is 0.6 meters, the equation becomes:

$$H_1 = \frac{0,6}{0,06} = 10 \text{ meter}$$

The width of the field is 10 meters which means the horizontal distance between the fields is 10 meters. The porch terraces will be made at a distance of 10 meters, planted with terrace reinforcement plants, such as ruminant grass or other grasses according to the wishes of the farmers. Terrace reinforcement plants are trimmed periodically, the results of the pruning are made into mulch to fertilize the soil or to feed ruminant animals, the dirt is put into the soil as organic fertilizer.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

1. The results of discharge measurements in the field indicate that the produced water discharge is around 1.48 liters/second, a volume that is estimated to be sufficient to irrigate 2.5 hectares of farming land.
2. The results of chemical analysis of water samples show that produced water fulfill water quality standards for irrigation, raw water, and fresh water
3. The results of soil chemical analysis showed that the soil reacted acid with a pH range between 4.17-4.66; low organic c; nutrients in nitrogen, phosphate, potassium, and sulfur are low; low cation exchange capacity (CEC). Micro nutrients such as Mn, Cu, and Zn are low except high grade iron.
4. Land in the research location is marginal land which is a general character of land that has undergone further weathering. If it is to be developed for farming, it requires management with the right technology by focusing on increasing the level of soil organic matter is about 5%, increasing the pH to more than 5.0, increasing the level of nutrients with fertilizers sourced from outside the soil-crop system.
5. For the development of organic vegetable farming, organic fertilizers required is about 40-60 tons/ha without the addition of inorganic fertilizers such as urea, SP-36, KCl, sulfur, and micro fertilizers.

Recommendations

Further research is needed to:

1. Identify and characterize all land in the Singa well, Lematang exploitation block, Muara Enim Regency, South Sumatra.
2. Design irrigation systems for agricultural land around Singa well, Lematang exploitation block, Muara Enim Regency, South Sumatra.
3. Develop demonstration plots of organic farming, especially organic vegetable crops.

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